

Week	Cell unacast	New York			California			Texas			Florida			Mississippi			Massachusetts		
	Dates	Average mobility	Non essential	Density	Average mobility	Non essential	Density	Average mobility	Non essential	Density	Average mobility	Non essential	Density	Average mobility	Non essential	Density	Average mobility	Non essential	Density
1	Jan 19-25	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	Jan 26-Feb 1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
3	Feb 2-Feb 8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
4	Feb 9-Feb 15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5	Feb 16-Feb 22	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
6	Feb 23-Feb 29	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
7	Mar 1-Mar 7	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
8	Mar 8-Mar 14	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
9	Mar 15-Mar 21	2	2	1	2	3	2	1	2	1	1	2	1	1	2	2	2	1	2
10	Mar 22-Mar 28	3	4	1	3	3	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	3	3	3	1	3
11	Mar 29-Apr 4	3	4	2	3	4	4	3	3	2	3	4	1	2	2	3	4	2	3
12	Apr 5-Apr 11	4	5	2	3	5	4	2	3	3	3	4	1	3	2	4	3	4	2
13	Apr 12-Apr 18	4	5	2	3	5	4	2	3	2	3	4	1	2	2	3	3	4	2
14	Apr 19-Apr 25	3	5	1	3	4	2	2	3	2	3	3	1	2	1	2	3	4	1
15	Apr 26-May 2	3	4	1	2	3	2	2	1	2	2	2	1	2	1	2	3	4	1
16	May 3-May 9	3	3	1	2	2	2	1	1	1	2	2	1	1	1	2	3	3	1
17	May 10-May 16	2	2	1	2	2	2	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	3	2	1	1
18	May 17-May 23	2	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1
19	May 24-May 30	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1
20	May 31-Jun 6	2	1	1	2	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1
21	Jun 7-Jun 13	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1
22	Jun 14-Jun 20	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
23	Jun 21-Jun 27	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
24	Jun 28-Jul 4	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
25	Jul 5-Jul 11	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
26	Jul 12-Jul 18	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
27	Jul 19-Jul 25	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
28	Jul 26-Aug 1	1	1	1	2	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1
29	Aug 2-Aug 8	2	1	1	2	1	2	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1
30	Aug 9-Aug 15	1	1	1	2	1	2	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1
31	Aug 16-Aug 22	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
32	Aug 23-Aug 29	1	1	1	2	1	3	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1
33	Aug 30-Sep 5	2	1	1	2	1	3	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1
34	Sep 6-Sep 12	2	1	1	2	1	3	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1
35	Sep 13-Sep 19	2	1	1	2	1	3	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1
36	Sep 20-Sep 26	2	1	1	2	1	3	1	1	2	2	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1
37	Sep 27-Oct 3	1	1	1	2	1	3	1	1	2	2	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1
38	Oct 4-Oct 10	2	1	1	2	1	4	1	1	2	2	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1
39	Oct 11-Oct 17	2	1	1	2	1	3	1	1	2	2	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1
40	Oct 18-Oct 24	2	1	1	2	1	3	1	1	2	2	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1
41	Oct 25-Oct 31	2	1	1	2	1	3	1	1	2	2	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1
42	Nov 1-Nov 7	2	1	1	2	1	4	1	1	2	2	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1
		55-70% decrease in distance >70% decrease in non-essential			40-55% decrease in distance 65-70% decrease in non-essential			40-55% decrease in distance 60-65% decrease in non-essential			40-55% decrease 60-65% decrease in non-essential			25-40% decrease <55% decrease in non ess			Da 40-55% decrease in first phase 65-70% decrease in non-essential		
		https://www.unacast.com/ocvd19/social-standing-scoreboard																	